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ПРОБЛЕМА ГУМАННОСТИ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ РАССКАЗАХ ДЛЯ ДЕТЕЙ

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Аннотация

Детская литература является уникальным средством отражения существующих в обществе идей. Ей принадлежит важнейшая роль в формировании культурного фона нации и каждого отдельного члена общества.

Процесс обновления, происходящий в материальной и духовной жизни нашего общества, непосредственно связан с изменением нашего взгляда на историю и теорию литературы, в том числе и детской.

Двадцать первое столетие ознаменовалось формированием в современной детской литературе многожанровой литературной системы. Предметом научного исследования в данной работе явились традиции и новаторство в русской детской литературе, составляющие значительный пласт в фольклорной и литературной традиции.

Ключевые слова Детская литература, аннотация, гумманность, жанр

Осмысление путей формирования новых жанров детской литературы как части единой жанровой системы до настоящего времени не было предметом специального изучения. В этой связи представляется весьма актуальной задачей исследование путей становления, формирования и эволюции жанров современной детской литературы, определение новаторской поэтики произведений для детей [1].

В диссертациях Нугыбаевой Г., Ибраимова Б., Розиевой Д. содержатся элементы теории детской литературы, в частности авторы поднимают вопрос о специфике характерных стилевых приемов творчества для детей.

Отдельно стоит отметить коллективную монографию «Детская литература в Казахстане: от дискуссий к решениям». Книга посвящена проблемам детского чтения и детской литературы в Казахстане; охватывает дискуссионные вопросы, касающиеся развития читательского интереса, а также включает анализ книжного рынка, в частности, издания оригинальной и переводной литературы для детей. Авторы монографии предлагают свое видение состояния и перспектив развития детской литературы в Казахстане и мире, а также предлагают пути решения проблем, связанных с культурой детского чтения [2].

Актуальность затронутой нами проблемы обусловлена художественной практикой. Современная жизнь отличается своей противоречивостью, сложностью, тревогой. В такой напряженной обстановке очень важно, чтобы книги, выпускаемые для детей, закладывали нравственные нормы и правила поведения в обществе. В этом плане немало делает современная детская литература, которая богата темами, поднимающими нравственные проблемы. Написанная по законам подлинного искусства, она удовлетворяет эстетические и этические потребности с учетом всех возрастов, начиная с дошкольного и кончая старшим школьным возрастом.

За последние годы в детской литературе появились новые имена детских прозаиков: Э.Н. Успенский, А.А. Усачев, Н.Веревошкин, С.Назарова, Л.Калаус, Л.Лазарева, Д. Джумагельдинова и другие. Уже первые их книги - неплохая творческая заявка на будущее. Написаны они с искренней любовью к детям, радуют пониманием

детской психологии, знанием жизни, интересов детей. Они учат доброте, чуткости, человечности, увлекательно рассказывают, казалось бы, о простых, будничных делах, в которых часто проявляются и характер человека, и его отношение к жизни [3].

Художественная литература, как никакая другая сфера общественного сознания, связана с процессом самопознания человека. Причем методы и формы образного воплощения новых представлений человека о себе в художественном творчестве наиболее органично и интегрально выражают границы и возможности человеческого сознания в абсолютном виде. Можно уверенно заявлять, что человек сегодня таков, каким и как изображают его в художественной литературе. Гуманистическая направленность литературы проявлялась всегда в том, что человек в ней, как в зеркале, видел процесс неуклонного расширения своих возможностей в защите добра [4].

Тема гуманности и дружбы занимает большое место в творчестве многих писателей, но особенно ярко она представлена в произведениях казахстанских писателей для детей. Как известно, писатель в обществе осуществляет роль духовного судьи, врача и священника одновременно. Наследуя эту позицию из традиционной культуры и культивируя ее на протяжении веков, он воплощает ее в особой, перформирующей функции слова как действенного средства преобразования реальности. Дружба являлась детских писателей той всепобеждающей силой, которая способна соединить на всю жизнь. Писатели показывают дружбу не только с людьми, но и животными. В произведении Нурдаулета Акыша «Мальчик, застеснявшийся собаки», автор рисует нам дружбу мальчика Куаныша и его пса Таймаса.

С доисторических времен собака живет бок о бок с человеком, немудрено, что за долгие века она успела занять прочное место и в литературе. В легендах, повестях, романах собака обычно играет ту же роль, что и в повседневной жизни: это верный спутник человека и его своеобразный ангел-хранитель.

Уже в «Одиссее» Гомер отводит собаке особую роль: старый пес по кличке Аргус оказывается единственным, кто узнает своего хозяина, вернувшегося после долгих скитаний.

В произведениях детской литературы упор делается на образ животного-защитника. Чаще всего в литературных произведениях собака довольствуется функциями помощника. Однако в произведении Нурдаулета Акыша собаке отводится роль главного судьи.

Чувство товарищества, верность, ответственность, преданность – все эти чувства пытался воспитать в Куаныше его отец.

С первых строчек мы видим радость ребенка от появления нового питомца.

Собака – верный друг и помощник человека, преданный ему по самой своей сути. На отношении к собакам проявляются человеческие качества: любовь и привязанность, в другом случае равнодушие и жестокость. Некоторые люди считают, что любовь к животным, в частности к собакам, порождает сентиментальность, слабость, а мы должны воспитывать сильных, смелых, твёрдых людей. Не понимают эти люди, что по-настоящему сильными и смелыми может быть лишь человек добра, может быть лишь гуманный человек. На отношении к собаке проявляются самые человеческие чувства – доброта, любовь и привязанность.

«Теперь большую часть свободного времени Куаныш проводит с Таймасом. Гладит его, играет с ним. Иногда он учит его находить брошенную вдаль палку. Но пока это у них не получается. Главная его обязанность – два раза в день давать Таймасу еду. Мальчик поначалу относился к этой работе с огромным вниманием и ответственностью, ведь он был так рад появлению собаки».

Образ собаки является центральным в данном рассказе. Служит связующей нитью между отцом и ребенком. «Папа назвал его Таймасом. Сказал: «Когда-то у меня была собака с такой кличкой».

Нравственно воспитанный человек никогда не сделает ничего плохого «братьям нашим меньшим». И даже этого бывает достаточно, чтобы осознать верность и любовь собак к людям.

Символичным является кличка собаки – Таймас. Это очень популярная казахская кличка для питомца, означающее –упрямый, упорный, не отступающий от своей цели. Не сойдет с правильного пути.ребенок, жизненный путь которого не оборвется, который не умрет; ребенок, который не будет поступать вопреки родительскому слову.

Появление Таймаса очень важный момент в жизни ребенка. У Куаныша меняется его взгляд на мир, открывая нам глубину переживаний ребенка.

«И тут Куаныш вспомнил, что, как назло, опять забыл дать ему еды. Как и в прошлый раз, он поспешил в дом, начал поспешно шарить в карманах, но не нашёл ключей. Он их утром дома забыл. Он посмотрел украдкой из-за угла дома на собаку, ожидающую, что, как и в прошлый раз, Куаныш вынесет из дома огромный кусок хлеба с маслом. Что же теперь делать? В кармане лежит мелочь. Значит, можно побежать в магазин и купить на неё полбулки чёрного хлеба. Но через ворота он не может выйти, потому что прямо у них лежит собака и она в нетерпении не сводит с него глаз. Нет, не может он решиться идти мимо пса с пустыми руками. А другой дороги на улицу нет. Немного подумав, Куаныш решил выйти наружу через соседский двор... И надо же такому случиться: перелезая через забор, он зацепился брюками за кол».

Сколько ни было историй, все они подводят ребенка к самому главному: пониманию ответственности перед питомцами. В ребенке пробуждается чувство ответственности за того, кто нуждается в защите и заботе.

К художественным особенностям прозы Патигуль Махсатовой можно отнести оригинальные приемы изображения жизненных ситуаций. Повествование ведется от имени девочки. Она описывает разумность животного и простодушного ребенка. Патигуль Махсатова постоянно сопровождают героев произведения «Верность» животными, которые сами являются главными персонажами, и вокруг них разворачиваются события. Они думают, веселятся, огорчаются, но при этом автор не уподобляет психику животного психологии человека, хоть они и наделены широчайшими душевными качествами. Мир животных – благородный, утонченный, нравственный. Животные не опускаются до ничтожества, никогда не предадут близкого существа. Сигнал – благородный герой. Он – олицетворение самых лучших человеческих качеств. В рассказах, написанных для детей, П.Махсатова более внимательно относится к житейской стороне жизни. Собака выдерживает экзамен на верность, человек – нет. «Горько и глубоко вздохнув, мама села в машину, а новые хозяева поразились, увидев, как из глаз Сигнала текут слёзы. Когда мама и родные, выехав из села, приблизились к холму, мой брат увидел бегущего вслед Сигнала. Путники продолжили путь, уверенные, что Сигнал, устав, отстанет от машины. Но даже через многие километры брат снова и снова видел на дороге бегущего Сигнала, который, как и положено верному псу, всегда был рядом. И лишь только у асфальтированной дороги, в двенадцати километрах, чёрный силуэт собаки словно растворился...». После всех своих злоключений Сигнал, в конце концов, попадает в руки своих старых хозяев.

Автор наделяет своих животных теми качествами, которые не помешали бы многим людям. Его герои-животные осознают, понимают намного больше, чем это дано человеку. Итак, мы видим, что с помощью приема отстранения, через образы животных, писатель рассказывает о насущных проблемах, затрагивает животрепещущие темы. Решение этих проблем остается за человеком, и все зависит только от него, от его выбора, от того, останется ли он Человеком с большой буквы – понимающим, сочувствующим, благородным, верным.

Взросление помогло понять лирическому герою, как она любит свою беззащитную слабую, старую собаку и вернуться к ней. Эти слова произносит для нас рассказчик, напоминая, что самые важные в жизни вещи – самые простые. И одной из них является мысль о глобальной ответственности каждого из нас. Только осознавая ее, можно в полной мере почувствовать себя счастливым.

«Почувствовав благодарность к преданному Сигналу, я задумалась о справедливости народной мудрости, которая гласит: «Собака – преданность, а женщина – обуза». Настало время прощания. Сигнал выглядел нерадостно. Похоже было, что жизнь его подходит к концу. Предчувствуя, что больше его не увижу, обняв его, я, в душе прощаясь, прокричала: «Сигнал, до свидания! Встречай, когда я приеду снова!» Но в следующий мой приезд я услышала, что Сигнал умер, уйдя на окраину села. Брат там же и предал его земле. Как говорится в народе, хорошая собака смерти своей никому не покажет. И опять моя собака поразила меня своей мудростью...»

«И люди вокруг нас стали другими. Те из них, которые при жизни брата были рядом, в одночасье изменились. Может, это только кажется, или я раньше этого не замечала. Мысль о том, что многие из окружения семьи теперь отвернулись от нас, разрывает моё сердце. В такие минуты я с благодарностью вспоминаю Сигнала, который был верен нам до последней минуты. Наверное, будь он жив, он, как когда-то, лизнув мои руки и произнеся взглядом: «Не плачь!», смог бы залечить мою израненную душу».

Красной нитью через рассказ проходит мотив верности. Собака выдерживает экзамен на верность, человек – нет. Эта мысль не дает покоя автору.

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PROSODIC ORGANIZATION OF SOUNDING DISCOURSE

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Abstract

Any language is a complex system of many elements, including the intonation system, which is realized in the prosodic organization of oral speech. Oral speech and the level of a person's proficiency in it determines his success and opportunities in a variety of activities. For this, the oral speech must have certain criteria related to the characteristics of the rhythmic-intonation side, certain intonation, pitch / loudness, rhythmic structure, and the setting of logical stress. These components, describing the peculiarities of the implementation of a syllable in sounding speech, are considered today as elements of prosody. The prosody characterizes the organization of the syllable sequence into a certain structural rhythmic-melodic unity. The theoretical foundations of the prosodic organization of sounding discourse, described from the point of view of their development in the works of linguistic researchers, are considered. It is noted that up to the present time, the oral discourse and its prosodic design have been insufficiently studied. In the article, oral discourse is understood as sounding speech as a social action accompanying a special speech interaction of people, influenced by the social context. Based on the analysis of scientific literature, it was revealed that it is prosody that is capable of imparting a certain stylistic and semantic coloring to a message in the process of sound discourse. It is possible to fully study the oral speech discourse only by relying on the elements of its prosodic structure.

Key words: prosody, speech discourse, prosodic organization, elements of the prosodic structure of sounding discourse.

Introduction

In modern society, the level of communicative competence has become one of the defining indicators of human development. One of the main linguistic skills that seems to be necessary for a specialist for development, both personal and professional, is the competent mastery of sounding discourse, especially in intercultural communications.

The first attempts to study sounding speech were made in ancient Greece and Rome. As noted by the Kazakhstani researcher Bazarbayeva Z. M., such figures as Aristotle, Demetrius, Demosthenes, Dionysius of Halicarnassus, Cicero, who studied oratory and taught eloquence and rhetoric, paid close attention to euphony, intonation of speech and the features and properties of individual sounds [1, p. 6].

Thus, the prosodic system of the language has long been an issue of interest to specialists in the field of public speech and recitation, which attached importance to the emotionally expressive, structural and logical features of sounding speech expressed with the help of prosodic means. Nevertheless, a separate science of the study of intonation - intology - formed only 80-100 years ago, and from a scientific point of view, the prosodic system of language in linguistic studies began to be considered much later.

Hence, the task of the work is to analyze the prosodic organization of the sounding discourse, made in the form of a literary review of the works of modern researchers.

The aim of the work is to consider the theoretical foundations of the prosodic organization of the sounding discourse, described from the point of view of their development in the works of linguists.

The research methods are a literature review, a comparative analysis of the ideas of the

authors under study.

The concept of "sounding discourse". We note a large number of definitions of the concept of discourse that exist at this stage in linguistics, which are united by the context of social communication carried out by communicants in the process of sound communication. An analysis of studies on modern discourse studies (the works of the authors N. D. Arutyunov, A. D. Belova, V. I. Karasik, O. O. Selivanova, etc.) leads to the identification of the main functional approaches of the authors to the definition of discourse and research its nature, formal, functional and situational. Since the sounding discourse of interest to us involves the implementation of speech as a purposeful, social activity under the condition of communication and interaction of people, a stable understanding of the sounding discourse becomes clear, which implies the participation of the speaker in social interaction.

When planning a practical study of a sounding discourse, it is necessary to analyze the work of linguists in order to identify the structural elements that characterize the object. As the analysis of the authors' works showed, in the classification of the elements of sound discourse, directions were identified according to which it is possible to characterize various functions that implement the functioning of sound discourse (dialogue discourse, pragmalinguistic, culturological, functional-speech, ethnographic). From the point of view of intercultural communication, it is considered as a complex phenomenon at the intersection of various sciences. Various researchers find contact of this concept with various sciences, linguistics, acoustics, ethnolinguistics, as well as with the theory and practice of translation. However, we are interested in the question of the prosodic organization of the sounding discourse.

In the works of researchers (Z. M. Bazarbayeva, L. G. Zubkova, A. A. Reformatsky, N. D. Svetozarova, S. S. Khromov, etc.) confirmation of the idea of changing the system of scientific analysis in modern linguistics of speech are found. Modern research theory and practice over the past two decades, especially in the linguistics of speech, requires a comprehensive, systematic consideration of the objects of scientific research, which is justified by the change in systematizing ideas in scientific research, which led to the change of level, stratified analysis, analysis is complex, polyfunctional. The idea is based on the trend of a sharp increase in the volume of oral speech in modern public speech practice, which at the same time contributed to the growth of technical capabilities based on the global spread of the Internet, social networks, and other forms of oral communication), and also set the task of "socialization and internalization of the individual in society" [2, p. one].

Thus, at the present stage, researchers have revealed a change in the communicative orientation of the speakers, and the transition from the installation from reading a pre-prepared text to a direct appeal to the communicants. And since already from antiquity, starting with the works of Greek philosophers-orators and up to the present time, the predominant influence of sounding speech on communicants (audience) in all sociolinguistic spheres has been revealed, this has led to an increase in the role of interpersonal communication, and putting forward the requirement to ensure the organization of modern sounding discourse in intercultural and interlingual areas.

We consider the sounding discourse as a special component of the system of oral communication in the process of intercultural interaction.

Any language is a complex system that includes many elements, one of which is the intonation system of the language, embodied in the prosodic organization of oral speech. In modern linguistics, this problem is given special attention, the question of the relationship between human speech activity, in which intonation and pronunciation play a crucial role, and the language system becomes relevant. Prosody is able to give the message a certain stylistic and semantic coloring. A full study of oral speech discourse is possible only when describing

the prosodic organization and variation of sounding speech.

Prosodic elements are realized at all levels of speech - in such segments as a syllable, word, syntagma, phrase, sentence, etc. Prosodic elements are a set of sound means by which phonemes (primary segment units) arranged in a certain sequence are combined into more complex intonational and semantic elements, such language units as words, syntagmas and utterances.

To date, the elements that make up prosody are indicated by various authors in different variations. Examining the degree of knowledge of the interpretation of the term, one can identify such opinions of authors as a group of researchers who distinguish between prosody and intonation and a group of scientists who advocate the inclusion of intonation in the composition of "prosodic components". Thus, the authors who own the point of view of combining intonation and prosody actually identify intonational components with prosody, and the term prosody itself is understood as "a system of pronunciation of stressed and unstressed, long and short syllables in speech" [3, p. 180–181].

Examples of such an understanding of prosody are, in particular, V. M. Solntsev, characterizing intonation as a prosodic means, [4, p. 152], A. A. Reformatsky as a "prosodic element of the language" [5, p. 191], and other authors. When studying prosody in the context of the structural organization of speech, L. V. Girinskaya describes prosody and its part, intonation [6, p. 279].

At the same time, these authors define prosody as a complex object, try to identify its essential features and characterize the structure of prosody.

Thus, in the works of M. A. Sokolova and other authors (K. P. Gintovt, I. S. Tikhonov and R. M. Tikhonov), such prosodic components of intonation as "pitch, loudness and tempo" are singled out [7, p. . 136], the authors replace the term intonation with the term prosody, which includes the indicated components.

As a result of the identification of the concepts of prosody and intonation, in these studies it was believed that such linguistic units as prosodemes and intonemes are identical [8, p. 73]. However, among researchers, both Russian and foreign, who support the point of view of combining the concepts of prosody and intonation, there are various provable ideas about understanding the essence of intonation. So, in the work of the researcher of the perception of English by ear, J. Brown, intonation is described as "a change in the direction of the speaker's voice tone", considering other speech criteria of the voice separately, referring them (for example, the categories of loudness, tempo, change in voice quality) to the criteria paralinguistic [9, p. 84]. The same opinion is also shared by other authors, when (in the work of A. Fox, D. Crystal and others) the difference between paralinguistic and prosodic criteria is also emphasized, as well as the absence of boundaries that make it possible to clearly distinguish between these concepts [10, p. 10], [11, p.180].

The founders of Kazakh intology are A. Baitursynov and K. Zhubanov, who worked in the 20-30s of the last century [1, p. 11]. A. Baitursynov, who laid the foundations of the prosodic system of the Kazakh language, studied stress and its functions as one of the most important elements of any language system, singled out languages with fixed and mobile stress. He noted the special melody of the Kazakh language, which distinguishes it from the Russian language, and made similarities, comparing its melodic-intonational structure with French. K. Zhubanov singled out the importance of intonation in speech communication, noting its following main functions: semantic, expressive-modal, communicative, semantic, syntactic and rhythm-forming [ibid, p. 12].

With the gradual development of science, various Kazakh philologists devoted their research to this topic, including S. Amanzholov [12], S. Kenesbaev [13], N.T. Sauranbaev

[14], T. Kordabaev [15], A. Nurmakhanova [16] and many others.

In works on Kazakh syntax and phonetics by S. Amanzholov, special attention is paid to the prosodic organization of speech, intonation and melodic of building various types of sentences in the Kazakh language. N.T. Sauranbaev emphasized that in the languages of the Turkic system, rhythmic, melodic and intonational language means play such a significant role that they determine a typologically especially constructed sounding speech, which differs in pronunciation and construction in its smoothness, melody and rhythm. This author singled out the stylistic and emotional functions of intonation - i.e. with the help of it, grammatical, expressive and semantic shades of phrases and sentences are transmitted [14, p. 28-30]. M. Balakaev and T. Kordabaev, who studied the syntax of the Kazakh language in a joint work, considering the prosodic organization of sentences in the Kazakh language, singled out intonation as the main indicator of any sentence. Researchers have noted that any sentence that sounds aloud is specific and individual in its intonational organization [15, p. sixteen].

S. Kenesbaev, who studied the phonetic system and prosodic organization of the Kazakh language, considered in detail such intonational element as stress. The scientist divided stresses into types - dynamic, tonic and phrasal, and also revealed its distinctive feature inherent in the Kazakh language - the function of phrasal-syntagmatic stress (separation of adjacent syntagmas) [13, p.280-281]. A. Nurmakhanova also considered in detail the meaning and characteristics of such a prosodic component as intonation, highlighting its two main functions. The first is emotional-expressive, when intonation conveys various expressive and emotional shades of speech, the second is syntactic-grammatical, which is responsible for differentiating different sentences [16, c.138-141].

Issues of Kazakh prosody, namely the problems of melody, accentuation, rhythm and pauses in Kazakh sounding speech, are also discussed in the works of Zh. Aralbaev. The scientist distinguishes three groups of languages based on stress: languages with mobile stress, with fixed stress and with stress fixed at the end of a word or syntagma. The first group includes the Russian language, where stress differentiates the meanings of words and word forms. An example of the second group is the Polish and Czech languages, in which stress plays a syllabic and word-identifying role. The third group are languages where the speech flow is divided into rhythmic segments, as in French.

However, of particular interest are the experimental phonetic works that were developed in the 1980-90s, devoted to the study of super-segment phonetics and intonation within the framework of the system-functional approach (Bazarbaeva, 1991, 1996)

According to Bazarbayeva Z. M., the phonetic system of the language is formed by segment and super-segment means. The segmental level is made up of phonemes (minimal sound units, from which words, morphemes, etc. are further formed), forming a linear structure of speech. Supersegmental means are intonational, they are superimposed on the phonemic structure of speech, forming the second line of sound.

Thus, the supersegmental level is a prosodic or intonational level, more complex in its structure. Supersegmental (prosodic) means function in the language simultaneously with speech flow segments.

The author, who devoted his main research into the intonation of the Kazakh language, confirms the complexity of the organizational structure and functioning of the intonation level of the language, called the prosodic level. At the same time, the researcher noted that the implementation of prosodic means in the speech flow is carried out with the help of changes in tone, dynamics, rhythm, and tempo of speech.

Thus, within the framework of the modern stage of language learning, prosody is considered as a set of supersegmental (rhythmic and intonation) properties of speech. The terms "prosodic" and "supersegmental" elements are synonymous in their meaning, but

nevertheless they emphasize two different aspects. The term "prosodic" indicates the nature of the sound means of the language, and "super-segment" emphasizes the correlation with more complex units.

In general, in the works of researchers studying the sounding discourse, the simultaneous presence in speech of linear (segmental) units (such as, for example, length) and suprasegmental sound features superimposed on linear units have been revealed.

Thus, the implementation of those and other units occurs "simultaneously with certain segment units" [17, p. 85]. In the work of Yu.S. Maslov, these suprasegmental sound features refer to prosodic phenomena that can be studied from the point of view of phonology, studying the functioning of these linguistic elements, which "in the language system are prosodic units - prosodemes" [17, p. 85-86].

The works of various researchers also describe the fact that phonological units are superimposed on segment ones (in the work on linguistics by Yu.S. Maslov, phonemes within a syllable are described as prosodemes, or "suprasegmental phonemes" [17, pp. 85-86]). In the works of V. A. Vinogradov, built on the principles of level-based scientific research, the language is considered at the segmental (phonemic) and supersegmental (prosodic) levels, noting that the regularities of the latter are less studied [18, p. P. 531], [19, p. 556], in 1977, 1990.

Researchers of the English language have also identified and supported the ideas of dividing language units into segmental and suprasegmental. So in the work of M.Ya. Bloch, (Theoretical Grammar, 2004) the first are phonemes that form chains of different levels (words, syllables, morphemes, etc.) [20, p. fifteen]. As for the second, suprasegmental units, M.Ya. Bloch notes their existence only in the process of implementation with segmental units, when they can express "various modification meanings or functions", which is reflected in the chains of the segmental level (here the author includes varieties of intonation, so-called "intonation patterns, stress and pause" [20, p. 16]).

In the works of specialists-researchers on the phonetics of modern English, the existence of suprasegmental phenomena in sounding speech is emphasized, covering both sounds and syllables and utterances, being subjected to stress (lexical and rhythmic), tone and intonation. Their authors characterize them as prosodic phenomena, highlighting their primary characteristic as "change in pitch at the level of utterance" [20, p. 17].

Regarding the functioning of intonation, the researchers noted that it is used to convey the intention of the speaker, to convey "how he wants his statement to be understood" [21, c 154].

At the same time, Webster's authoritative encyclopedic dictionary classifies pitch, stress, tonal junction, nasalization, the presence or absence of voice in combinations as suprasegmental units, and calls them "prosodemes". Prosodemes, according to the dictionary, contribute to the maintenance of speech communication "accompanying a sequence of segmental phonemes (vowels and consonants), which are assembled into a certain structure" [22, p. 2299].

Thus, based on the study, we can conclude that the prosodic and intonational organization of the sounding discourse differ in their functional specificity, nevertheless, the intonation is included in its prosodic structure. Both the prosodic and intonational organization of the sounding discourse belong to the units of the suprasegmental level.

Summing up, it should be noted that the prosodic structure, the most important elements of which are stress and intonation, organizes such sound sequences as syllables, words, syntagmas, utterances, phrases. The concept of intonation also includes the content side, while prosody is basically a means of systemic organization of speech units. On the other hand, prosody is still wider than intonation, since it is implemented on all segments of

the speech chain. Intonation, on the other hand, organizes only utterances and syntagmas. So prosodic can be called the "building material" of intonation.

The prosodic characteristics of speech are correlated with units larger than the phoneme. As prosodic characteristics, such signs as duration, frequency and intensity of tone, as well as characteristics of the intonation-semantic articulation of speech, the transfer of emotional and communicative meanings are used.

Based on the indicated components of prosody, it is possible to present the parameters necessary for consideration to characterize the prosodic organization of any sounding discourse.

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ZONING REGULATION AS LAND USE CONTROL INSTRUMENT

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Abstract: Zoning is used to regulate the use of land in cities and other settlements, agricultural land and lands, the protection of which is necessary for nature conservation purposes. The increased attention to the legal regulation of territorial zoning is due to the fact that the system for determining the legal regime of the land, which has been in place for many decades, is no longer up to date. Prior to the adoption of the Land Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, it was considered that in order to establish a legal regime for the land, it was sufficient only to carry out a purposeful division of land into certain categories. Zoning was seen as a supportive tool for clarifying the legal regime of certain categories of land.

Key words: zoning of territories, urban zoning, categories of land, land legislation

Land zoning issues are interdisciplinary and intersectoral. This trend is becoming more pronounced. But the basic and fundamental provisions on this issue have been enshrined in a special codified act - the Land Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan [1]. The starting point is provisions that reveal the nature, purpose and tasks of rational use and protection of land. The system of zoning rules is first of all subject to the principles of land law, predetermining the tendencies of their further development. Thus, to article 4 of the Land Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan land legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan shall be based on the following principles: 1) integrity, inviolability and inalienability of the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan; 2) preservation of the land as a natural resource, living and activity bases of the people of the Republic of Kazakhstan; 3) protection and rational use of lands; 4) safety ecologic provision; 5) intended land use; 6) priority of agricultural lands; 7) provision of information about lands condition and its accessibility; 8) state support of the activities for use and protection of lands; 9) prevention of endamage to the land or removal of its consequences; 10) serviceability for land use.

Thus, S.B. Baysalov, while researching the principles of water law, refers to them the basic, guiding principles that permeate all institutions of the industry and are reflected in one way or another in all its norms [2, p.144].

According to N.B. Mukhitdinov, the principles of law are the leading beginnings of its formation, development and functioning, which are generally binding for all and permeate the legal reality of the country as a whole. The most important feature of the principles of law is that they express not only existing attitudes, but also progressive tendencies of development of society, and therefore include policy requirements, starting ideas-objectives [3, p.110].

Thus, A.H. Hadjiyev, the system of principles of land law has a number of regulatory and functional qualities: directly regulates land relations; acts as a means of overcoming gaps and contradictions in the regulation of a specific land legal relationship; defines the main directions, serves as a guideline for rule-making and improving law enforcement; ensures the consistency of land legal regulation; serves as a legal indicator of compliance of land policy with socio-economic interests of subjects of land legal relations [4, p.36].

In the conditions of formation of the land legislation of the transition period, the principles enshrined in the land legislation of preservation of land as a natural resource, the basis of life and activity, ecological safety of the people of the Republic, rational use of land, The priority of agricultural land is objectively conditioned, and the legal regulation of zoning relations must be in line with it.

At the same time, the development of principles of zoning of the territory as a relatively independent institution, research of their relationship with other principles, determination of their place in the hierarchy of principles of land law acquires particular relevance in the domestic land science, which is important for understanding the specifics of land-legal regulation of land zoning relations.

Clear definition and consistent stipulation in land legislation of the fundamental principles, principles of land zoning, ultimately, it should contribute to the progressive realization of the goals and objectives of legal security and land protection as the main objective of land law.

Legislative attempt to specify the general principles of land legislation in the area of zoning of the territory was made in the Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan «On the basic provisions and principles of zoning of the territory» of October 10, 1997, as amended by the Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan of 28.08.2001 №1123 (SAAP of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 1997., №46, art.425).

According to the Decree, zoning of agricultural land is based on the following principles: priority of agricultural land; special protection of agricultural land; targeted use of agricultural land; Compensation for losses in agricultural production when agricultural land is removed for non-agricultural purposes.

Zoning of land of settlements (cities, towns and rural settlements) is based on the following basic principles: use of land of cities, towns, rural settlements in accordance with their master plans, Planning and development projects and land management plans of the territory; the separation of suburban areas outside the city limits with defined use.

In suburban zones, zoning of the territory is carried out with the allocation of zones of intensive development of suburban agricultural production, especially urban planning (reserve areas for urban development, installation and construction of facilities necessary for the normal functioning of engineering and transport infrastructures), green areas occupied by forests, forest parks and other green spaces, performing protective and sanitary-hygienic and recreational functions of the population.

Zoning of industrial, transport, communications and other non-agricultural lands is carried out in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan regulating relations on the use and protection of land, subsoil, environmental protection, other legislative and regulatory acts and is based on the following basic principles: ensuring rational, integrated and safe use of land and subsoil; ensuring environmental protection Wednesday; creating the necessary conditions for the functioning of industrial, transport and other facilities, as well as performing tasks in the field of strengthening the country's defense capability; establishing zones around industrial, transport and other facilities with special conditions for the use of land, within which the body that made the decision to grant land ownership or land use restricts or prohibits those activities that incompatible with the purposes of establishing zones.

In zones with special conditions for the use of land, the following are defined: sanitary protection zones of industrial enterprises; mudslide, landslide and protective forest zones adjacent to after the diversion of railways and highways; protective zones of water intake structures; aerodrome strips; security zones of trunk pipelines, communication lines, radio and power transmission; water protection zones and strips; territory of military polygons.

Zoning of lands of specially protected natural territories, lands of recreational, recreational and historical and cultural purposes is carried out in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the field of environmental protection and is based on the following basic principles: conservation of the state nature reserve fund, biological diversity and natural ecological systems; targeted use of specially preserved natural territories; rational use of specially protected natural territories for the development of science, culture, education and education; development of tourism and recreation, taking into account socio-economic factors and the interests of the local population; state support for the use and protection of specially protected natural territories; state regulation and control in the field of specially protected natural territories; payment for the use of specially protected natural territories; compensation for damage caused by violation of legislation on specially protected natural territories.

Zoning of forest fund lands is carried out on the principles of: providing conditions for increasing the ecological and resource potential of forests; rational and sustainable use of forest resources, their protection, protection and reproduction; compensation for losses of forestry production caused by the withdrawal of forest lands for their use for purposes unrelated to forestry and agriculture or deterioration of land quality in as a result of the influence caused by the activities of enterprises, organizations and citizens.

Zoning of water fund lands is carried out on the following basic principles: ensuring rational use of water for the needs of the population, economic sectors and the environment; protection of water resources from pollution, clogging and depletion; prevention and elimination of harmful effects of water.

The zoning of reserve lands is carried out on the principle of prospective determination of the target regime of lands not granted ownership or land use for the needs of agriculture, industry and other purposes.

It should be noted that the principles set forth in the Government Resolution only establish the characteristics of the zoning of certain categories of land and do not reflect the general requirements for the zoning of the territory regardless of their categorical affiliation, which means essentially a return to the position of the former Soviet legislation, which considered the elements of zoning as an auxiliary instrument in determining the legal regime of individual categories of land.

In our view, the full functioning of the Institute would be facilitated by the consolidation in the land legislation of the country's single land fund and its constituent parts of fundamental requirements reflecting the legal nature, the functional designation of zoning regulations, as a necessary and independent component of the legal regulation of land relations.

The analysis of domestic and foreign legislation on the problems of land zoning leads to the conclusion that it is necessary to enshrine as such the necessity of zoning the land fund of the country and all its constituent parts and the regulatory nature of zoning acts, Scientific validity, objectivity, accessibility of acts of zoning of the territory, optimal combination of state, public and private interests in zoning of the territory, complex solution in zoning of ecological, social and economic problems of the territory. In addition, they have been reflected, albeit in a fragmented manner, in the land-based legal acts of systemically important importance. Thus, the Land Code stipulates the need for zoning at the district, regional and national levels, and defines the bodies responsible for its implementation.

The binding nature of the zoning of the land fund and its regulatory and legal nature implies, first of all, the zoning of all constituent parts of the land fund, regardless of the categorical ownership, forms of ownership and management of it, Creation of a detailed system of material and procedural guarantees for its conduct, with a clear statement of the

rights and obligations of all participants in the zoning law, organizational and legal forms of coordination of their activities, sources of financing. The obligatory nature of zoning and its regulatory-legal nature means also that the special regime of the use of territories determined by zoning, considered and approved in the manner stipulated by the legislation, is mandatory for subjects of land relations.

Affirmation of the scientific validity, objectivity and accessibility of zoning acts as a fundamental requirement requires, first of all, a clear definition of the scientific basis, responsibility and competence of the relevant subjects involved in their formation, the legal value of the information collected. In accordance with the current land legislation, the definition of zones is carried out on the basis of data from land, urban planning and other cadastres, aerial photography materials, soil, geobotanical and other surveys and surveys, as well as programs for the rational use of land, excess soil fertility, protection of land resources and in combination with other environmental measures, market conditions, prospective economic forecasts.

Land zoning data, containing information on the target use of territories, are used in the organization of land administration, the resolution of land disputes, the provision of land to private ownership and land use, seizure (redemption) land for state needs, issuance of permits for the occupation of land for exploration, control over the use and protection of land and other purposes related to the regulation of land relations. The accessibility of zoning acts also implies the establishment of a detailed system of legal guarantees of the rights of citizens and public associations to information in accordance with the provisions of the Aarhus Convention.

The need to consolidate as a principle of zoning the optimal combination of state, public and private interests follows from the qualitative changes of the Land Law of sovereign Kazakhstan, which has been transformed from a purely public sector to a public-private sector in the market. In the current legislation, the need to take into account the interests of the State and the population was reflected only in urban planning legislation. So, according to Article 3 The Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan on architectural, urban planning and construction activities in the Republic of Kazakhstan [5] the main areas of activity in the field of architecture, urban development and construction should ensure the state, public and private interests in this sphere:

state interests - interests of society as a whole in ensuring conditions of sustainable development of regions, cities, towns, villages (villages) and other settlements, functioning of life support systems, transport and engineering communications, communication and energy, environmental protection, preservation of historical and cultural heritage sites;

public interests - the interests of the population of certain regions, cities, towns, villages (villages) and other settlements in ensuring favourable living conditions (stay) on this territory, improving the environmental situation, preventing dangerous (harmful) Impacts resulting from economic and other activities, development of the infrastructures of settlements and adjacent areas, preservation of historical and cultural heritage objects, natural values;

private interests - interests of individuals and legal entities in connection with the implementation of architectural, urban planning and construction activities on their land plots.

Urban planning and building activities of citizens and legal entities may be restricted if they create inconvenience or impossibility of using, owning or disposing of them (used by them). It is important for the effective application of land legislation in the area of zoning that it enshrines as a basic principle a comprehensive solution to the ecological, socio-economic and zoning problems of the territory. In accordance with the Guidelines for the development of district zoning schemes, approved by the Order of the Chairman of the Land Administration Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan of 29 December 2004, 107-P, the

zoning of land takes into account the following factors: Natural and economic conditions; the purpose of the land; the quality of the land, its productivity and assessment; the ecological state of the land; the special or special use of land of different categories and others.

It seems that the complex solution of zoning ecological, socio-economic problems of the territory should be considered in several aspects: 1) the complex nature of the tasks addressed during land zoning; 2) the complexity of the work on zoning of the territory as a set of various types of organizational, scientific and technical and other activities; 3) the complex nature of the legal regulation of the relations that arise in the zoning of the land. The specificity of the legal regulation of land zoning is the unacceptability of the traditional approach, limited to narrow interests of rationalization of land use within certain categories of land. On the basis of the existing relationship in nature and the interdependence of its individual elements, it is necessary to regulate the whole complex of relations that arise during the zoning of the territory.

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